

Kinetic Evidence for the Enol Intermediate in Oxidation of Isopropyl Methyl Ketone and Isobutyl Methyl Ketone by Bromamine-T in Perchloric Acid Media

BHARAT SINGH*, (Miss) DEEPIKA SINGH, RAJENDRA CHAND and A. K. SINGH

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002

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The oxidation kinetics of isopropyl methyl ketone (IPMK) and isobutyl methyl ketone (IBMK) by acidic solution of bromamine-T (BAT) show zero order dependence on BAT and first order on both ketones and H^+ . No effect of *p*-toluenesulphonamide (TSA) was evident. The observed stoichiometry, zero effect of ionic strength and a solvent isotope effect ($k_0D_2O/k_0H_2O=2.04-2.32$ at 35° , $2.16-2.42$ at 40° for IPMK, and $1.80-2.18$ at 35° , $1.89-2.24$ at 40° for IBMK oxidations) point to a mechanism involving catalysed enolisation of ketones in the slow and rate determining step, followed by its subsequent fast interaction with BAT giving final products. Activation parameters and isolation of products are in agreement with the proposed mechanism.

BROMAMINE-T (BAT) is a potent oxidising agent and has been used in the estimation of several organic compounds¹. Some investigations involving oxidation of alcohols²⁻⁴ by acidic solution of BAT in the presence of Ru^{III} as catalyst have recently been reported but its mode of oxidation is still unprobed for uncatalysed reactions. Oxidation kinetics of aliphatic, cyclic and aromatic ketones by various other oxidants have been reported⁵⁻¹¹ earlier. The present paper reports the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of the title ketones by acidic solution of BAT.

Experimental

The materials employed were of highest purity available. The ketones, chloramine-T and perchloric acid (all E. Merck), *p*-toluenesulphonamide (Koch-Light) were used. All other reagents were of AnalaR grade. BAT solution was prepared and standardised by the method described in earlier^{1, 2}, and stored in a black-coated bottle. The reaction stills were blackened from outside and double-distilled water was used throughout the experiments. Deuterium oxide (purity 99%) was supplied by B.A.R.C., Bombay.

The reactions were carried out under [BAT] $\ll$ [Ketone] conditions, *i.e.* rates were measured with excess ketone over BAT. The reaction was initiated by rapid addition of BAT solution to the temperature-equilibrated ketone-acid mixture with vigorous shaking and the reactions were followed upto 75% of the reaction by the iodometric estimation of the unreacted BAT at various time intervals. The rate coefficients were reproducible within $\pm 2.8\%$.

Results and Discussion

The reaction mixture containing a known excess of [BAT] over [Ketones] in varying ratios was

allowed to equilibrate at 35° in presence of $0.02 M HClO_4$. The estimation of unconsumed [BAT] revealed 1:3 and 1:2 stoichiometry between IPMK and BAT and between BAT and IBMK as shown in equations (1) and (2), respectively.

where, R represents $i-C_4H_9$ and R' represents $i-C_3H_7$ groups.

The end-products, acids (yield $\sim 82\%$) in equation (1) and 1,2-diketone (yield $\sim 88\%$)¹² in equation (2) were identified by adopting the followed by conventional spot-test analysis¹³. 1,2-Diketone was also identified through dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNP) derivative¹⁴.

A six-fold variation in [BAT] at 35 and 40° (Table 1) shows zero order dependence on BAT. This was further supported through the plots of the remaining [BAT] and time at varying concentrations of BAT, which produced parallel lines (Fig. 1). Zero effect of ionic strength variation (affected by $NaClO_4$) and TSA (one of the reaction products) variation was observed and recorded (Table 1).

First order dependence on each [ketone] and $[H^+]$ ions was observed, which was obvious from the slope values (nearly one) of the straight lines obtained from $\log k_0$ vs $\log$ [ketone] plots (Fig. 2, A and B) and $\log k_0$ vs $\log [H^+]$ plots (Fig. 2, C and D). The overall second order rate constant k_2 , calculated as $k_2 = k_0/[ketone][H^+]$, were found to be 13.48, 18.12; 5.44, $7.68 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 35 and 40° for IPMK and IBMK oxidations, respectively. The reactivity order, IPMK $>$ IBMK is explained on the basis of the steric factors¹⁵ operative in the neighbourhood of the ketonic group. The larger

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF [BAT], [TSA] AND IONIC STRENGTH (μ) VARIATION ON REACTION RATE

[HClO₄]=5.00×10⁻³ M, [Ketone]=10.00 (IPMK) and 5.00 (IBMK)×10⁻³ M

[BAT] ×10 ³ M	$k_o \times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$			
	IPMK		IBMK	
	35°	40°	35°	40°
0.80	6.11	9.16	1.98	1.95
1.04	6.72	9.07	1.99	1.95
1.20	6.80	9.10	1.40	1.98
2.00	6.64	9.06	1.96	1.92
2.56	6.92	9.24	1.98	1.92
4.00	6.00	9.12	1.40	1.93
4.80	6.24	9.06	1.39	1.96
4.00 ^a	6.02	9.14	1.98	1.92
4.00 ^b	6.04	9.10	1.39	1.94
4.00 ^c	6.00	9.08	1.40	1.90
4.00 ^d	6.04	9.12	1.38	1.92
4.00 ^e	6.01	9.10	1.99	1.90
4.00 ^f	6.02	9.12	1.37	1.93
4.00 ^g	6.00	9.08	1.40	1.94
4.00 ^h	6.03	9.14	1.38	1.92

[TSA]=^a1.50, ^b2.00, ^c3.00, and ^d5.00×10⁻³ M. Ionic strength (μ)=^e6.00, ^f9.00, ^g12.00, ^h15.00×10⁻³ M.

Fig 1. Zero order plots at 40°: [isobutyl methyl ketone]=5.00×10⁻³ M, [HClO₄]=5.00×10⁻³ M, and [BAT]₀: (A) 0.80, (B) 1.04 (C) 1.20, (D) 2.00, (E) 2.56, (F) 4.00 and (G) 4.80×10⁻³ M.

the alkyl group in a particular substrate the slower is the rate of its oxidation.

Table 2 records the kinetic results obtained at 30, 35, 40 and 45°. The values of energy of activation (ΔE^*) and entropy of activation (ΔS^*) are respectively 68.00 kJ mol⁻¹ and 108.15 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ for IPMK and 82.91 kJ mol⁻¹ and 67.28 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ for IBMK oxidations. The solvent isotope effect (D₂O-H₂O in different ratios) was studied (Table 2). Addition of radical scavengers like allyl acetate (upto 0.02 M) did not influence the oxidation rate.

Fig. 2. Plots of log k_o vs log [ketone]: (A) [HClO₄]=5.00×10⁻³ M, [BAT]₀=1.04×10⁻³ M, temp.=35° (IPMK), and (B) [HClO₄]=5.00×10⁻³ M, [BAT]₀=0.80×10⁻³ M, temp.=40° (IBMK). Plots of log k_o vs log [H⁺] (C) [IPMK]=4.00×10⁻³ M, [BAT]₀=1.04×10⁻³ M, temp.=35°; and (D) [IBMK]=4.00×10⁻³ M, [BAT]₀=0.80×10⁻³ M, temp.=40°.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF SOLVENT ISOTOPE AND TEMPERATURE VARIATION ON REACTION RATE

[BAT]=1.04×10⁻³ M, [Ketone]=4.00×10⁻³ M, [HClO₄]=4.00 (IPMK) and 13.34 (IBMK)×10⁻³ M

Temp. °C	D ₂ O-H ₂ O v/v. (%)	$k_o \times 10^7 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
		IPMK	IBMK
35	0-100	1.59	2.16
40	0-100	2.24	3.03
45	0-100	3.54	3.94
50	0-100	5.48	5.52
35	30-70	3.25	3.90
35	50-50	3.40	4.25
35	70-30	3.69	4.71
40	30-70	4.84	5.72
40	50-50	5.12	6.14
40	70-30	5.42	6.78

Singh *et al.*^{8,4,16} reported that the following equilibria exist in acidified BAT solution,

where, Ts stands for CH₃C₆H₄SO₂⁻ and TSA for TsNH₂. It appears from equilibria (3-6) that the probable oxidising species of BAT in acidic media are TsNHBr, TsNBr₂ and HOBr. Soper¹⁷ reported that [HOCl] is very small in acidified chloramine-T solution and is independent of chloramine-T. Similar conclusions can also be drawn for [HOBr] in acidified BAT solution and thus any role of HOBr as an oxidant seems to be unlikely. The remaining species, *i.e.* either TsNHBr or TsNBr₂ appears to be the real oxidising species of BAT. It is not possible to establish the predominance of one

species over the other with the present kinetic data. Zero order dependence of the reaction on BAT suggests its involvement in fast steps preceded by the slow and rate controlling enolisation step and thus does not contribute any way either in distinguishing or identifying either of the two remaining species as real oxidising species of BAT. Therefore, it seems unconvincing to use either TsNHBr or TsNBr_2 as oxidant in the present case. Under the circumstances and with the present kinetic results BAT as such has been shown as an oxidant in the reaction mechanism. This also explains the zero effect of TSA which is formed after the slow and rate determining step (ii).

Ketones are known to enolise in acidic media as

where, S represents the ketone, S' the conjugate acid and S'' its enolic form. The kinetic observations and above statements suggest that BAT is involved in fast steps after the slow and rate determining enolisation step. Such contention also finds support from the work of Littler and Waters¹⁸. The following reaction paths are suggested for the acid catalysed oxidation of both the ketones (S) by BAT,

slow and rate determining step,

(Intermediate species)

Application of the steady-state treatment to [S'] with the approximation $k_2 \ll k_{-1}$ (because (ii) is the slow step) yields the rate law as

$$\frac{-d[\text{BAT}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1 k_2}{k_{-1}} [\text{S}][\text{H}^+] \quad (8)$$

The rate law (8) is in agreement with kinetic orders and the proposed mechanism is supported by solvent isotope effect. Substantial deuterium isotope effect accords well with carbonium ion character in the transition state (equation 7). This indicates and confirms that oxidation takes place through enol form and not through keto form of the ketone. The overall reaction may be pictured as given below in the oxidation of both the ketones (where, R is $i\text{-C}_2\text{H}_5$ group in IMBK and IPMK).

References

1. C. G. R. NAIR and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1976, 23, 239.
2. B. SINGH, A. K. SINGH, N. B. SINGH and B. B. L. SAXENA, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, 40, 5203.
3. B. SINGH, A. K. SINGH, R. K. SINGH, N. B. SINGH and B. B. L. SAXENA, *Natl. Acad. Sci. Lett.*, 1983, 6, 265.
4. B. SINGH, N. B. SINGH and B. B. L. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 319.
5. P. S. RADHAKRISHNAMURTHI and S. DEVI, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, 10, 496.
6. P. NATH and K. K. BANERJEE, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1976, 29, 1939; *Can. J. Chem.*, 1970, 48, 2414.
7. R. SANEHI, M. C. AGRAWAL and S. P. MUSHAN, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, 255, 293.
8. B. SINGH, P. K. SAXENA, R. K. SHUKLA and B. KRISHNA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 56.
9. B. SINGH, P. K. SAXENA, M. RICHARDS and B. KRISHNA, *Z. Phys. Chem. (Leipzig)*, 1978, 259, 801.
10. B. SINGH, L. PANDEY, J. SHARMA and S. M. PANDEY, *Tetrahedron*, 1982, 38, 169.
11. B. SINGH, A. K. SAMANT and B. B. L. SAXENA, *Tetrahedron*, 1982, 38, 2591.

12. J. MUKHERJEE and K. K. BANERJI, *J. Org. Chem*, 1981, 46, 2323.
13. F. FRIGL, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", Elseviers, Amsterdam, 1966, p. 325.
14. I. VOGEL, "Elementary Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmans Green, London, 1958, Part-III, p. 79.
15. R. T. MORRISON and R. N. BOYD, "Organic Chemistry", Prentice Hall, London, 1971, p. 473.
16. B. SINGH and R. CHAND, *Tetrahedron*, 1985, 41, 2371.
17. F. G. SOPER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1899.
18. J. S. LITTLE and W. A. WATERS, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 827.